

The Role of Work Satisfaction in Mediating the Influence of Performance Benefits and Organizational Fairness on Employee Performance at Puskesmas Banjarangkan I Klungkung Regency

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ABSTRACT

The Puskesmas Banjarangkan I in Klungkung Regency is one of the health service units contributing to providing healthcare services to the community. However, the minimum performance targets have not yet been achieved. The important idea that emerges is to convey the significance of performance allowances and organizational fairness to increase employee satisfaction and thereby enhance their performance. The purpose of the research is to reveal how work satisfaction mediates the influence of performance allowances and organizational fairness on employee performance at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I in Klungkung Regency. This study applies a quantitative approach, using surveys and a sample of 78 employees from the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency. The analysis employs the PLS-based SEM method and measures the scale using a quantitative approach similar to that used in earlier studies. The study's results show that performance allowances and organizational fairness have a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction and performance. Employee satisfaction also has a positive and significant influence on performance, and it can mediate the impact of performance allowances and organizational fairness on employee performance. Additionally, organizational fairness tends to determine employee performance. I would suggest that the management of Puskesmas Banjarangkan I improve the decision-making process that involves employees. This includes exploring the job description and listening to employee problems before creating decisions. It is also important to gather accurate and complete information before making any decision.

KEYWORDS: Performance Benefits, Organizational Fairness, Work satisfaction, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Puskesmas is one of the most important health service units that contribute to providing comprehensive and integrated services to the people in its working area. In other words, the health center has the authority and responsibility for the healthcare community in that specific region. This emphasizes the importance of Puskesmas's role in providing health services to the community. All stakeholders involved must strive to improve their performance and provide the highest quality of service professionally and optimally. One of the critical components that strongly support the provision of good health services to society is the human resources of the organization. This is especially crucial in the Health Center of Banjarangkan District, Klungkung Regency.

It is crucial to measure the performance of health workers at Puskesmas to achieve the standard Minimum

Services (SPM) in the Health Sector. These provisions ensure the minimum quality of basic services as government affairs to fulfill the rights of every citizen, in accordance with the provisions set by the government for each applicable SPM target. The target is expected to reach 100%, leading to enhanced people's welfare (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2018). The SPM targets are planned performance activities that require inputs and processes carried out over a period of time. These activities include health program processes such as individual and community service activities, management activities, and capacity development activities (Gani, 2018). However, the target of achieving the minimum standard for the performance of health service employees in three years from 12 SPM has never been reached according to the overall target of 100%. In the last three years, the achievement of SPM at the

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Puskesmas Banjarangkan I has continued to decline. Performance is essential for every agency, including the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I. It reflects an agency's ability to manage and allocate employees, and employee performance has a significant impact on the agency's ongoing activities and the attainment of its objectives. Gibson (2017) identified three factors that can affect performance. The first factor is individual characteristics including abilities, skills, family background, work experience, social status, and demographics. The second factor is psychological, which includes perception, role, attitude, personality, motivation, and work satisfaction. The third factor is organizational, which covers organizational structure, job design, leadership, and reward system (Gibson, 2017). There are three things that are the focus of this research are factors of organizational fairness, performance allowances, and work satisfaction related to employee performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance allowance as a form of reward given to employees for their work. According to Handoko (2017) that performance allowances are any additional benefits offered to workers or employees such as the use of company vehicles, free lunches, health services, holiday assistance and so on, so allowances are additional compensation aimed at binding employees to keep working for the company. According to Simamora (2016) performance allowances are any additional benefits offered to workers or employees such as the use of company vehicles, free lunches, health services, holiday assistance and so on. So, the allowance is additional compensation that aims to bind employees to keep working for the company.

Organisational fairness is a concept used to describe the important role of fairness as it directly relates to the work environment. To be precise, organisational fairness relates to employees' perceptions of whether they have been treated fairly at work or otherwise (Eberlin & Tatum, 2015). Organisational fairness reflects the extent to which people feel that they are treated fairly at work. Employees who feel

injustice in the workplace can show a variety of negative behaviours and can affect employee commitment to the organisation and performance implementation (Rubianingsih, 2017).

Work satisfaction is an important point in an employee's self that describes one's feelings towards the work being carried out. These feelings will later be reflected in their behavior in the work environment and outside the work environment. According to Handoko (2016) work satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state of how employees perceive their work. Work satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work. Another opinion regarding work satisfaction Hasibuan (2016) states that work satisfaction is an emotional attitude that pleases and loves his job. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline and work performance.

Performance is the result of carrying out a job, both in nature physical/ material and non-physical/ non-material (Nawawi, 2015). Meanwhile, according to Wirawan (2016) performance is output generated by the functions or indicators of a job or a profession at any given time. According to Mangkunegara (2016) performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with responsibility assigned to him. Performance can be interpreted as achievement or operational effectiveness an organization and employees based on goals, standards and pre-defined criteria. Performance refers to levels achievement of the tasks that make up an employee's job. Performance reflects how well employees meet requirements a job. Performance is often misinterpreted as *effort* which reflects the energy expended (Simamora, 2017).

HYPOTHESIS MODELS

The hypothetical model of the role of work satisfaction in mediateing the influence of performance benefits and organizational fairness on employee performance at Puskesmas BanjarangkanI, Klungkung regency, as following :

Figure 1. Research Hypothesis Model

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Based on the research hypothesis model above, the hypothesis in this study is as follows: Implementation of performance allowance policies positive effect on employee work satisfaction; Organizational fairness has a positive effect on employee work satisfaction; Implementation of performance allowance policies positive effect on employee performance; Organizational fairness has a positive effect on employee performance; Work satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance; Work satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of implementing performance allowance policies to employee performance; Work satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of organizational fairness to employee performance

METHOD

Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire. The population size in this study was 78 people Puskesmas Banjarangkan I staff. The sampling technique used is a saturated sample something method For choose all population is sampled .

The research questionnaire was prepared based on the results of studies and theoretical and empirical formations

during the pre-research, first assessing the validity of the face and content, sentence and structure of each question through discussions with several employees of the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency . In the process, several improvements were also made to the content of the questions in the research instrument. Furthermore, the try out involved 30 respondents to ensure the level of validity and reliability of the research instrument before it was distributed to all intended respondents. If the research instrument has been declared valid and reliable at this trial stage, then the research instrument is said to have good calibration for each variable measure studied. Then the research instruments were distributed directly to all target samples. Data obtained from the distribution of research instruments as a whole. Then examined, tabulated, filtered, and analyzed to answer and discuss research problems.

RESULTS

Based on the results of tests carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 application, an image of the research model can be presented as follows:

Figure 2. Full Structural Model (PLS Bootstrapping)

The results of testing the research hypothesis based on the picture above are as follows:

Hypothesis Testing 1: Allowances performance (X₁) proved to have a positive effect on employee work satisfaction (Y₁). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.157 with a T-

statistic = 4.375 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 1 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 2: Organizational fairness (X₂) proved to have a positive and significant effect on employee work satisfaction (Y₁). This result is indicated by the path

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coefficient which has a positive value of 0.932 with T-statistic = 49.831 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05) . Based on this, hypothesis 2 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 3 : Allowances k performance (X_1) proved to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.079 with T-statistic = 3.332 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.001 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 3 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 4: Organizational fairness (X_2) proved to have a positive and significant effect to employee performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.350 with T-statistic = 5.752 (T-statistic > 1.96) with p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 4 is declared accepted .

Hypothesis 5 testing: Work satisfaction (Y_1) is proven to have a positive and significant effect to employee performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.632 with T-statistic = 9.552 (T-statistic > 1.96) with pvalue = 0.001 . Based on hypothesis 5 it is declared accepted .

Satisfaction work (Y_1) able to mediate on the indirect effect of performance allowances (X_1) on employee performance (Y_2). These results are shown from the mediation test that was carried out, it appears that the effects C, D and A have significant values as well the indirect effect path coefficient obtained is > 0.10, which is 0.100 (Hair et al., 2014). The results of this study determine that performance allowances (X_1) can affect employee performance through the role of work satisfaction can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the application of the performance allowance policy at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, the better the work satisfaction employees will increase so that it will have an impact on increasing employee performance. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of the satisfaction variable Work on the indirect effect of performance allowances on employee performance partial. These findings provide clues that the work satisfaction variable (Y_1) is not a determining variable in the effect of performance allowances (X_1) on employee performance (Y_2) (Partially Mediated) .

Satisfaction work (Y_1) able to mediate on the indirect effect of organizational fairness (X_2) on employee performance (Y_2). These results are shown from the mediation test that was carried out, it appears that the effects C, D and A have significant values as well the indirect effect path coefficient obtained was > 0.10, which was 0.589 (Hair et al., 2014). The results of this study determine that organizational fairness (X_2) can affect employee performance through the role of work satisfaction can be proven

empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the justice received by employees then employee work satisfaction will increase so that it will have an impact on increasing employee performance. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of the application of work satisfaction variable (Y_1) on the indirect effect of organizational fairness on employee performance partial. This finding indicates that the variable work satisfaction (Y_1) is not a determining variable in the effect of organizational fairness (X_2) on employee performance (Y_2) (Partially Mediated) .

Organizational fairness (X_2) on employee performance (Y_2) has the greatest total effect, namely 0.939 compared to the performance allowance (X_1) path on employee performance (Y_2), which only obtains a total effect of 0.179. These results provide an indication that employee performance tends to be determined by fairness organizational implementation that is implemented in the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, this shows that when employee believe that they has treated with fair, they are tend show performance more work increase.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the analysis, this section will discuss the results of the calculations that have been carried out. This study aims to determine the impact of mediating the implementation of patient safety on safety culture and communication and its effect on the performance of nurses in the Bali Provincial Mental Hospital . Testing is shown through existing hypotheses so as to find out how each variable influences other variables.

The Effect of Implementing Performance Allowance Policies on Employee Work satisfaction at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency

Based on results analysis about the effect of implementing performance allowance policies on employee work satisfaction, shows that performance allowances proved to have a positive effect on employee work satisfaction. These results indicated that hypothesis 1 (H_1) was accepted. Findings This give meaning the better the policy implementation performance allowance will increase employee work satisfaction. Implementation of performance allowance policies provided by agencies Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency expected can increase performance employee. Provision of performance allowances in the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency which is perceived to be commensurate with the workload and has been able to meet the needs of workers so that performance allowances become a driving force for employees to be more enthusiastic at work because when employee accept perceived performance gain comparable with fair and proper in accordance with the responsibilities, employees will obtain work satisfaction to achieve organizational goals.

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Work benefits as something that is received as a substitute for their services to the company and the provision of benefits is one of the implementation of the human resource management function which relates to all kinds of individual awards in exchange for carrying out organizational tasks is good, companies that provide benefits to each employee in accordance with the position of employees in the company, the existence of office facilities provided by the company which are felt to have been able to support employee work activities properly, and the existence of employees who get praise and recognition from the leadership if employees have achieved good work results, has made employees feel comfortable and in accordance with the burden and tasks that have been given by the organization in the field of work so that employees will be happier and love their work

The results of this study are in line with the results of research by Zulkifli (2018) about the effect of work benefits on employee work satisfaction at the human resources center apparatus . Results research shows that work benefits have a positive and significant effect on employee work satisfaction. Another study, by Safiudin (2021), the results of this study also show that performance allowances have a positive and significant effect on work satisfaction at CV. Satria Bumi Artha in Probolinggo. Purnamasari's research (2019) also found that there was a positive influence significant difference between benefits on Employee Work satisfaction at PT. Eliza Parahyangan Garut Sub Branch

The Effect of Organizational fairness on Employee Work satisfaction at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency

Based on results analysis about influence organizational fairness to employee work satisfaction, shows that organizational fairness proved to have a positive and significant effect on employee work satisfaction, results testing This show that hypothesis 2 (H₂) is accepted. The results of the analysis obtained gives the meaning that the better the employee's perception of organizational fairness will increase employee work satisfaction . Good organizational fairness can be felt by employees with it implementation of a salary system in accordance with workload, reflecting salary employee contributions, and salary received according to performance. Reward procedures and regulations, application is also good and consistent without any discrimination. Subordinates feel treated with courtesy, dignity, transparent in communication, and superiors fully explain the rules, and communicate with subordinates whenever necessary, communication effective relationship between superiors and subordinates. Of course, it will increase work satisfaction employee. It shows justice implemented properly and had a positive impact and significant to work satisfaction. The better the fairness

implemented by the organization, the better the satisfaction employee's perceived work.

This is in line with Sareshkeh's research (2017) which states that good perceptions of organizational fairness by employees in organizations will increase the positive emotions of these employees. Employees who feel that their organization has provided justice, these employees will do their job with a sense of joy and positive. Naem et al. (2018) is of the view that every employee wants There is fairness in the work environment, such as fair procedures used in terms of setting rewards, distributing rewards and interacting with superiors will be able to make them more satisfied

Increasing employee work satisfaction can be done with fair procedures and results in the work environment (Hasmarini, 2018). If justice is given by a company to its employees, indirectly employees feel satisfied with their work because there is no comparison between them. According to Sareshkeh (2017) concluded that the higher the sense of justice felt by employees, the higher the satisfaction of these employees will be followed.

This result support study from Sethi et. al. (2017) stated that organizational fairness has a positive effect on work satisfaction. The results of this study are also supported by Thorn's research (2017) which states that the higher the fairness that employees feel from their organization, the higher their satisfaction with their work.

Influence Implementation of Performance Allowance Policies on Employee Work Performance at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency

Based on results analysis about implementation of performance allowance policies on employee performance, shows that implementation of performance allowance policies proved to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, results testing This show that hypothesis 3 (H₃) is accepted. This finding means the better the implementation of the policy performance allowance will improve employee performance. Implementation of performance allowance policies provided by agencies Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency expected can increase employee performance allowances. This expected along with achievements to be proud of , benefits performance is one implementation gift compensation or well deserved reward on performance or in a word another allowance performance is award form addition given income to employee on performance with objective for increase Spirit Work employee .

The results of this study are supported by Purnamasari (2019) which states that performance allowances are basically a tool for realizing the vision and mission of the organization with the aim of creating a formal bond of cooperation between the organization and employees within the organizational framework, directing abilities, skills, time, as well as energy which is all aimed at work

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satisfaction, providing stimulation and motivating employees to give the best performance. Meanwhile, according to Permatasari (2020) Performance allowances are only one of several factors that can affect performance, performance allowances are influential because the tasks they are doing are given appreciation or prizes to give them more enthusiasm in carrying out their tasks, however, employees must be able to account for what they are doing, after being given performance allowances it does not mean they are careless in carrying out their duties or work, they must provide good performance.

Research results This in accordance with research conducted by Kusuma (2018) about the effect of work benefits, motivation and work satisfaction on employee performance at the Office of the High Religious Court of Samarinda. Results research shows that work benefits have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Another study, by Hamidun (2017) the results of this study also show that performance allowances have a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the Tuminting District Office, Manado City . Permatasari's research (2020) also found that there was a positive influence There is a significant difference between allowances on the performance of nurses in the Inpatient Room of the Laburan Baji Hospital

The Effects of Organizational fairness Against Employee Performance at Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency

Based on results analysis about organizational fairness against employee performance, shows that organizational fairness is proven to have a positive and significant effect to employee performance, results testing This show that hypothesis 4 (H₄) is accepted. this result give meaning the better the employee's perception of organizational fairness will improve employee performance. This shows that respondents have a perception of justice that is felt as a decision-making mechanism that involves employees so as to improve the accuracy of information and reduce the occurrence of bias in the opinion of supervisors and processes from the approach itself including *the job description* , superiors listen to employee problems before creating them decision, superiors seek accurate and complete information before making decisions, superiors provide information before needed by employees, work decisions applied consistently and employees are free to express opinions on work decisions can improve employee performance.

The results of this study are in accordance with the theory Theodosi (2018) organizational fairness is really needed by employees with the aim of employees being even more enthusiastic at work. Therefore, companies must pay attention to their employees fairly, attention is given by giving justice to each employee by means of superiors

treating employees equally in the organization, besides that employees are given fair service marks for the work that employees have given by the company and employees. involved in decision making by giving employees the opportunity to voice their opinions. The positive impact is that after employees get organizational fairness, employees will feel valued and be even more active at work. This really supports improving employee performance, besides that employees will give dedication to the company wholeheartedly because the company has given its obligations to each of its employees fairly.

These findings are also supported by Tamrin's research (2018) showing that organizational fairness has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the Kendari State Islamic Institute. Another study, by Kristanto (2017) the results of this study also show that organizational fairness has a direct and significant effect on the performance of CV Tanaya Fiberglass employees, Surabaya.

Influence Work Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Based on results analysis about effect of work satisfaction on employee performance, shows that work satisfaction proved to have a positive and significant effect to employee performance, results testing This show that hypothesis 5 (H₅) is accepted. This result give meaning that the better work satisfaction then the performance will increase this can be caused by a company always carry out system career and compensation with well, there is good relationship between colleague work, attitude always the boss motivating, as well environment work conducive physique will convince employee become feel safe and comfortable work. Impact is, employee will Work with best and always try give service the best to customers, such p show that performance employee the high.

This findings in accordance with theory Hasibuan (2016) work satisfaction is attitude emotional fun and love of job. Fun job in accordance with desire employee will make employee feel comfortable in work, so performance will the more. Besides party promotions of leader with work performance will make employee feel his job appreciated will make they feel satisfied and them will increase performance so you can achievement in work. According to Luthans, (2016) work satisfaction is an important factor in influencing employee performance, this is because work satisfaction in employees at work can foster a boost of motivation and morale within him to show better performance. Thus, it can reduce disruptions and obstacles as well as non-fluency in all processes within the organization. Luthans regarding the factors of work satisfaction, namely the work itself, salary, promotion policies, supervision, and work groups.

Researchers have recognized interest this, so that we get lots studies which designed for evaluate impact satisfaction on productivity, absence and discharge

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employee. No doubt Again that work satisfaction related significant with performance employee. Asthu (2017) suggests that part manager assume that satisfaction Work Which tall forever will raises performance high, but insurance no right, proof which give impression become more accurate that productivity that possible satisfaction. Robbins and Judge (2018) explain that employee which no satisfied can so is employee w high produce high, currently or low and they will tend forward level performance which raises satisfaction for them. Connection satisfaction with performance employee more complicated rather than statement simple that satisfaction raises performance. Opinion in on show that no can generalized that if employee satisfied with his job, certain will perform high. In case certain there is possibility though employee satisfied will but performance not enough fulfil standard which set. This matter significant that performance employee no only influenced variable which very varied.

Role Work satisfaction in Mediating The Effect of Implementing Performance Allowance Policies on Employee Performance at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency

Based on results analysis shows that work satisfaction able to mediate the indirect effect of implementing performance allowance policies on employee performance. The results of this study found that performance allowances can affect employee performance through the role of work satisfaction can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the application of the performance allowance policy at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, the better the work satisfaction employees will increase so that it will have an impact on increasing employee performance. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of the satisfaction variable Work on the indirect effect of performance allowances on employee performance partial. These findings provide clues that the satisfaction variable Work not as a determining variable on the effect of performance allowances on employee performance.

The results of this study were reinforced by Syed et al (2018) several factors for workers to feel satisfied, including promotions, supervisory behavior, work environment, performance and job benefits, and life conflicts, as one of the main assets in the company, workers must be able to manage properly in order to remain productive, one of which is by providing appropriate performance allowances. Employee work satisfaction will increase if allowance performance implemented well, will produce satisfaction perceived work employee so that increase performance employee.

Study earlier carried out by Ayunia (2019) found the effect of performance allowances on work satisfaction indicating that performance allowances have a positive and significant effect on work satisfaction of contract workers.

This means that the higher the compensation given to workers, the higher employee work satisfaction will be. The existence of performance allowances for employees is felt to be commensurate with the workload and has been able to meet the needs of workers so that compensation can be an incentive for contract workers to be more enthusiastic at work. The results of this research are Kurniawan, et al. (2018) on PT Prudential Life Assurance Malang employees who stated that compensation has a positive and significant relationship with worker work satisfaction, because when workers receive compensation that is felt to be comparable to the sacrifices that have been made it will make these workers feel satisfied.

Role Work satisfaction in Mediating The Effects of Organizational fairness On Employee Performance at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, Klungkung Regency

Based on results analysis show satisfaction work is able to mediate the indirect influence of organizational fairness on employee performance. The results of this study determine that organizational fairness can influence employee performance through role satisfaction work can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the justice received by employees then employee work satisfaction will increase so that it will have an impact on increasing employee performance. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of the application of work satisfaction variables on the indirect effect of organizational fairness on employee performance not as a determining variable on the influence of organizational fairness on employee performance.

The results of the analysis also found that fairness organizational on employee performance has the greatest total effect compared to the Performance Allowance channel on employee performance . These results provide an indication that employee performance tends to be determined by organizational fairness implementation that is implemented in the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, this shows that when employee believe that they has treated with fair, they are tend show performance more work high. Another finding obtained that organizational fairness influence has an indirect effect on performance through work satisfaction greater than the direct effect of organizational fairness to performance. This shows that perception employee about fairness own impact positive and vital inside increase satisfaction they likewise on employee performance. Fulfillment created organization or institution in a manner no direct will influential to satisfaction employee on the job they do. Employees work satisfaction, reflected in attitudes positive that employees give to his job with carry out not quite enough answer in a manner fine, here will increase desire employee for develop yourself and survive in organization during maybe.

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The success of a company or agency is largely determined by the performance of its employees in various fields. The role of employees in any business is an important factor. Therefore, companies or agencies must be able to manage human resources, namely employees in such a way that there is a balance for all employees in a company or agency. The balance created is in the form of organizational fairness. Equity theory explains that distributive and procedural justice refers to employees' perceptions of fairness and the balance between the input they provide in the form of education, training, experience, and the rewards they receive. Thus, employees will tend to ask for remuneration according to what they do (Widiastuti & Aisyah, 2018). The fulfillment of justice created by companies or agencies will indirectly affect employee satisfaction with the work they do. Employee work satisfaction, reflected in the positive attitude that employees give to their work by carrying out their responsibilities properly, satisfaction within each employee can be grown by companies or agencies by implementing organizational fairness as best as possible (Widiastuti & Aisyah, 2018).

Employee satisfaction with the company or agency is expected to improve the performance of employees in achieving the goals of the company or agency where they work. Employee satisfaction with the company or agency is expected to improve the performance of employees in achieving the goals of the company or agency where they work. The results of the study (Widiastuti & Aisyah, 2018) prove that work satisfaction mediates the effect of procedural justice and performance. Other results such as research (Praditya & Putra, 2018) prove work satisfaction mediates the effect of procedural justice and organizational commitment and research results (Suharyoko, 2017) prove work satisfaction mediates the influence of organizational fairness and employee performance. Fu & Deshpande (2018) proved that work satisfaction has an effect on employee performance in insurance companies in China.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion of research results it can be concluded that:

Performance allowance proved to have a positive effect on employee work satisfaction. this result give meaning that the better the policy implementation performance allowance will increase employee work satisfaction; Organizational fairness proved to have a positive and significant effect on employee work satisfaction. this result give meaning the better the employee's perception of organizational fairness will increase employee work satisfaction; Performance allowances influential positive and significant to performance employee. this result give meaning that the better policy implementation performance allowance will improve employee performance; Organizational fairness influential positive and significant to

employee performance. This result give meaning the better the employee's perception of organizational fairness will improve employee performance; Work satisfaction proven influential positive and significant to peg a wai performance. this result give meaning the taller employee work satisfaction to his job will increase performance employee in implementation task to be not quite enough he replied. Organizational fairness structure has the greatest total effect compared to the performance allowance channel on employee performance; Work satisfaction capable mediate on influence not direct performance allowances to performance employee. this result give meaning the better the implementation of the performance allowance policy at the Puskesmas Banjarangkan I, the better the work satisfaction employees will increase so that it will have an impact on increasing employee performance; Work satisfaction able to mediate the indirect influence of organizational fairness on employee performance. this result give meaning the better the justice received by employees then employee work satisfaction will increase so that it will have an impact on increasing employee performance and fairness organizational on employee performance has the greatest total effect compared to the performance allowance channel on employee performance.

SUGGESTION

Some suggestions that can be given related to the results of this study include: Research results show that organizational fairness have greatest total effect to to performance employees where procedural fairness indicators gets the highest weight compared to other indicators, so it is suggested to improve decision-making mechanisms that involve employees so as to improve the accuracy of information and reduce the occurrence of bias in the opinion of supervisors and processes from the approach itself including *the job description* , superiors listen to employee problems before creating them decisions, seeking accurate and complete information before making decisions, superiors provide information before needed by employees, work decisions applied consistently and employees are free to express opinions on work decisions

Implementation of performance allowance policies at the Banjarangkan Health Center Already good enough with be measured with a number of indicator so that the implementation of performance allowance policies to performance employees , but indicators The principle of fairness is the indicator with the lowest score, so it is recommended that management in implementing performance allowance policies pay attention to the principle of fairness, fairness does not mean that every employee receives the same amount of performance allowance, but the provision of benefits should be adjusted to work performance, type of work, job risk, responsibility and position. work

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Satisfaction of reward is the lowest indicator of the variable work satisfaction, so for increase employee work satisfaction to work which can later improve employee performance so that this requires efforts : Consider performance benefits in accordance with the efforts that have been made by employees, responsibilities and workload; Providing fair opportunities for employees to attend trainings to improve employee performance; Provide a fair opportunity for employees to study in detail the new tasks that will be carried out by each employee. Other researchers can do study qualitative For study more deep about performance employee.

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